

Identification of new studies via databases and registers

Identification

Records identified from:
Lens.org (n = 385)

Screening

Review data
(n = 385)

Records removed before screening:
Duplicate records (n = 93)

Title/Abstract screening
(n = 292)

Records excluded
(n = 89)

Full text screening
(n = 203)

Records excluded
(n = 65)

Included

Studies included for data extraction
(n = 138)

